

Studies in Chromones and Flavones. Part X*: Syntheses of some Acenaphtho- γ -Pyrones.

T. C. THOMAS and SURESH SETHNA

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M.S. University, Baroda-2

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5-Hydroxy-4-acetylacenaphthene on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation and benzoylation gave 2'-methylacenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone and 2'-phenyl-3'-benzoylacenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone respectively. 2'-Phenylacenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone and its 4'-methoxy derivative have been synthesised by the condensation of 5-hydroxy-4-acetylacenaphthene with benzaldehyde and anisaldehyde respectively and subsequent bromination of the acenaphthyl styryl ketones formed to get the dibromides and treatment of the dibromides with potassium cyanide.

5-Methoxy-4-formylacenaphthene on condensation with o-hydroxyacetophenone gave o-hydroxy-phenyl β (5-methoxy-4-acenaphthyl) vinyl ketone which was cyclised to 2'(5'-methoxy-4'-acenaphthyl) benzo- γ -pyrone by heating its dibromide with potassium cyanide.

IN continuation of our work on acenaphthene derivatives¹ we have now studied the synthesis in some acenaphtho γ -pyrones.

5-Hydroxy-4-acetyl acenaphthene² on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation gave a product which analysed for $C_{18}H_{14}O_3$. Therefore, 2'-methyl-3'-acetylacenaphtho(5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone (Ia) structure is assigned to the product. Trivedi, Sethna and Shah³ have shown that the formation of 3-acyl γ -pyrones is a common feature of the Kostanecki-Robinson acylation. On boiling with anhydrous sodium carbonate in alcohol this product gave the desired 2'-methyl acenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone (Ib). 5-Hydroxy acenaphthene on refluxing with ethyl acetoacetate in diphenyl ether according to Desai *et al.*⁴ gave the same product.

5-Hydroxy-4-acetyl acenaphthene on Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation gave a product to which 2'-phenyl 3'-benzoyl acenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone structure (Ic) is assigned on the basis of analytical data. However, the debenzoylation could not be achieved. On refluxing with anhydrous sodium carbonate in alcohol, the original compound was recovered and on refluxing with alcoholic sodium hydroxide, 5-hydroxy-4-acetyl acenaphthene was obtained. Bhullar and Venkataraman⁵ have made a similar observation in the case of naphtho γ -pyrones. Another approach to the synthesis of 2'-phenyl acenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone was therefore tried.

5-Hydroxy-4-acetylacenaphthene was condensed with benzaldehyde in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide. The product obtained gave blue colour with alcoholic ferric chloride, a deep red colour with conc. sulphuric acid and a positive Wilson test.⁶ Moreover, it gave an acetyl derivative when refluxed with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride. 5-Hydroxy-4-acenaphthyl styryl ketone (IIa) structure is assigned to the ketone. It was cyclised to 2'-phenyl acenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') pyran-4'-one (IIIa) by refluxing with alcoholic hydrochloric acid. Attempts to

convert the ketone to the desired γ -pyrone by refluxing in iso-amyl alcohol with selenium dioxide did not succeed. Acenaphthene itself gives various oxidation products when heated with selenium dioxide⁷. The ketone (IIa) was therefore brominated with one mole of bromine and the dibromide was cyclised to 2'-phenylacenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone (Id) by refluxing with alcoholic potassium cyanide.

5-Hydroxy-4-acetyl acenaphthene on a similar condensation with anisaldehyde gave 5-hydroxy-4-

acenaphthyl *p*-methoxy styryl ketone (IIb). This ketone was cyclised to 2'-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)acenaphtho(5,4 : 6',5')pyran-4'-one (IIIb) by refluxing in alcohol with hydrochloric acid. The ketone was brominated with one mole of bromine and the dibromide was cyclised to 2'-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)acenaphtho(5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone (Ie) by refluxing with alcoholic potassium cyanide.

A chromone derivative with acenaphthyl group in the 2-position has also been synthesised. 5-Methoxy-4-formyl acenaphthene¹ was condensed with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone in the presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide. *o*-Hydroxyphenyl β -(5-methoxy-4-acenaphthyl)vinyl ketone (IV) structure is assigned to the product as it gave a colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, an intense red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid and a positive Wilson test. The ketone was cyclised by refluxing with alcoholic hydrochloric acid to 2-(5'-methoxy-4'-acenaphthyl)benzopyran-4-one (V). The ketone (IV) was brominated and the dibromide obtained was converted into 2-(5'-methoxy-4'-acenaphthyl)benzo γ -pyrone (VI) by refluxing with alcoholic potassium cyanide.

Experimental

2'-Methyl-3'-acetylacenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone : 5-Hydroxy-4-acetylacenaphthene (1.5 g.) was refluxed with freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) and acetic anhydride (6 ml.) in an oil bath at 180°-90° for 15 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured on ice and the separated solid crystallised from alcohol in shining flakes (0.4 g.), m.p. 214°. (Found : C, 78.09; H, 4.98; C₁₈H₁₄O₃ requires C, 77.71; H, 5.03%).

2'-Methylacenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone : A mixture of the above γ -pyrone (0.5 g.) in alcohol (25 ml.) and anhydrous sodium carbonate (3 g.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 3 hr. The solvent was removed by distillation and the mixture was diluted with water. The product obtained crystallised from alcohol in light yellow needles (0.15 g.), m.p. 227°. (Found : C, 81.01; H, 5.24. C₁₆H₁₂O₂ requires C, 81.36; H, 5.08%).

The same compound was obtained when 5-hydroxy-acenaphthene (1 g.) was refluxed for 2 hr. with ethyl acetoacetate (1 ml.) in diphenyl ether (10 ml.) with a short air condenser so that the water and alcohol formed were removed and the solvent was then removed by steam distillation.

2'-Phenyl-3'-benzoylacenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone : 5-Hydroxy-4-acetylacenaphthene (2 g.) mixed with sodium benzoate (3 g.) and benzoic anhydride (6 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 180°-90° for 15 hr. The mixture was then poured on ice and kept overnight. The pasty mass obtained was repeatedly boiled with water to remove the sodium benzoate and unreacted benzoic anhydride. The solid obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow flakes (0.8 g.), m.p. 259°-60°. (Found : C, 83.65; H, 4.63. C₂₈H₁₈O₃ requires C, 83.50; H, 4.47%).

5-Hydroxy-4-acenaphthyl styryl ketone : A mixture of 5-hydroxy-4-acetylacenaphthene (2 g.) in alcohol

(40 ml.), benzaldehyde (3 ml.) and potassium hydroxide (log. in 10 ml. water) was kept at room temperature for 48 hr. It was then diluted and acidified with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained crystallised from petroleum ether in red prisms (1.1 g.), m.p. 186°. (Found : C, 83.88; H, 5.41. C₂₁H₁₆O₂ requires C, 84.01; H, 5.33%).

This compound gave a deep red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid, a positive Wilson test and a blue colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The acetyl derivative : The above ketone (0.8 g.) was refluxed with freshly fused sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.) on a sand bath for 1 hr. It was then poured on ice and left overnight. The solid obtained crystallised from petroleum ether. M.p. 110°. (Found : C, 80.96; H, 5.08. C₂₃H₁₈O₃ requires C, 80.70; H, 5.26%).

2'-Phenylacenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') pyran-4'-one : 5-Hydroxy-4-acenaphthyl styryl ketone (1 g.) in alcohol (75 ml.) was refluxed with conc. hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) on a steam bath for 48 hr. The solvent was removed and the mixture was diluted with water. The product obtained crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 191°-92°. (Found : C, 84.12; H, 5.17. C₂₁H₁₆O₂ requires C, 84.01; H, 5.33%). Mixed m.p. with 5-hydroxy-4-acenaphthyl styryl ketone was depressed by over 16°. It did not give the Wilson test and gave no colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

5-Hydroxy-4-acenaphthyl styryl ketone dibromide : 5-Hydroxy-4-acenaphthyl styryl ketone (1 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (15 ml.) and bromine (0.5 g.) dissolved in chloroform (5 ml.) was added at 10°-15° drop by drop with constant stirring. After the addition, the solution was kept at 10°-15° for 2 hr. The solvent was allowed to evaporate. The residue crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in yellow needles, m.p. 112°. (Found : Br, 34.91. C₂₁H₁₆O₂Br₂ requires Br, 34.77%).

2'-Phenylacenaphtho (5,4 : 6',5') γ -pyrone : The above ketone dibromide (1 g.) in alcohol was refluxed with potassium cyanide (1.5 g.) on a steam bath for 1 hr. The solid obtained on removal of the solvent and addition of water crystallised from benzene. M.p. 254°-55°. (Found : C, 84.22; H, 4.69. C₂₁H₁₄O₂ requires C, 84.57; H, 4.69%).

5-Hydroxy-4-acenaphthyl *p*-methoxy styryl ketone : A mixture of 5-hydroxy-4-acetyl acenaphthene (1 g.) anisaldehyde (1 ml.) and potassium hydroxide (5 g. in 5 ml. water) in alcohol (50 ml.) was kept at room temperature for 48 hr. The dark red solution was then diluted with water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solid was filtered and washed several times with sodium bicarbonate. The residue crystallised from benzene in red prisms (0.4 g.), m.p. 163°. (Found : C, 80.13; H, 5.43. C₂₅H₁₈O₃ requires C, 80.00; H, 5.45%). It gave a positive Wilson test, a deep red colour with conc. sulphuric acid and a colour with ferric chloride.

The methyl ether : The above ketone (0.5 g.) was refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.5 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.8 g.) in acetone (30 ml.)

on a steam bath for 3 hr. The solvent was removed and the reaction mixture was diluted with water. The product was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 154°. (Found: C, 80.68; H, 6.12. $C_{23}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 80.23; H, 5.81%).

2'-(*p*-Methoxy phenyl) acenaphtho (5,4:6',5')pyran-4'-one: 5-Hydroxy-4-acenaphthyl *p*-methoxy styryl ketone (1 g.) was refluxed in alcohol (75 ml.) containing hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) for 36 hr. on a steam bath. The solvent was removed by distillation and the mixture was diluted with water. The product that separated was crystallised from petroleum ether in yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 152°. (Found: C, 79.64; H, 5.29. $C_{22}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 80.00; H, 5.45%).

Mixed m.p. of the compound with the styryl ketone was depressed by about 18°. This compound did not give the Wilson test.

5-Hydroxy-4-acenaphthyl *p*-methoxy styryl ketone dibromide: 5-Hydroxy-4-acenaphthyl *p*-methoxy styryl ketone (1.1 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (15 ml.) and bromine (0.5 g.) in chloroform (5 ml.) was added dropwise at 10°–15° with stirring. The mixture was kept at 10°–15° for 2 hr. The product obtained on removal of the solvent was crystallised from petroleum ether in yellow needles (0.9 g.), m.p. 153° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 32.60; $C_{22}H_{18}O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 32.65%).

2'-(*p*-Methoxy phenyl) acenaphtho (5,4:6',5') γ -pyrone: The above dibromide (1 g.) and potassium cyanide (2 g.) were refluxed in alcohol (50 ml.) for 1 hr. on a steam bath. The solvent was distilled off and the mixture was diluted with water. The solid obtained crystallised from benzene in yellow prisms (0.7 g.), m.p. 242°. (Found: C, 80.50; H, 4.98. $C_{22}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 80.48; H, 4.87%).

β -(5-Methoxy-4-acenaphthyl) vinyl *o*-hydroxyphenyl ketone: A mixture of 5-methoxy-4-formylacenaphthene (1 g.), *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (0.6 ml.) and potassium hydroxide (5 g. in 5 ml. water) in alcohol (50 ml.) was kept at room temperature for 48 hr. The solution became deep red in colour. It was then diluted and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid with proper cooling. The solid obtained was filtered and crystallised from benzene in yellow needles (1.1 g.), m.p. 168°. (Found: C, 80.50; H, 5.70. $C_{22}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 80.00; H, 5.45%). This compound gave a positive Wilson test, a deep red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid and a brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The acetyl derivative: The above ketone (0.5 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (3 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (1 g.) on a sand bath for 1.5 hr. The product crystallised from petroleum ether in light yellow needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 100°. (Found: C, 77.66; H, 5.66. $C_{21}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 77.41; H, 5.37%).

2-(5'-Methoxy-4'-acenaphthyl) benzopyran-4-one: The above ketone (1 g.) in alcohol (75 ml.) and conc. hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) were refluxed on a steam bath for 48 hr. The solvent was removed by distillation and the mixture was diluted with water. The solid obtained crystallised from alcohol in light yellow needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 150°–51°. (Found: C, 80.22; H, 5.17. $C_{22}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 80.00; H, 5.45%). It did not give the Wilson test and gave no colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

β -(5-Methoxy-4-acenaphthyl) α - β -dibromo ethyl *o*-hydroxyphenyl ketone: β -(5-Methoxy-4-acenaphthyl) vinyl *o*-hydroxyphenyl ketone (1.1 g.) in chloroform (15 ml.) was treated with bromine (0.5 g.) in chloroform (5 ml.) dropwise at 10°–15° with stirring. After completing the addition the mixture was stirred for further 2 hr. The solvent was allowed to evaporate and the residue was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in light yellow needles (0.9 g.), m.p. 143°. (Found: Br, 32.60. $C_{22}H_{18}O_3Br_2$ requires Br, 32.65%).

2-(5'-Methoxy-4'-acenaphthyl) benzo- γ -pyrone: The above dibromide (1.5 g.) in alcohol (100 ml.) was heated with potassium cyanide (3 g.) on a steam bath for 1 hr. The solvent was distilled and the residue was diluted with water. The solid obtained crystallised from alcohol in light yellow needles, m.p. 152°. (Found: C, 80.28; H, 4.98. $C_{22}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 80.48; H, 4.87%).

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